

Preliminary Study on the Questionnaire for the Evaluation of Psychotherapy (Q-EPT)

Giovanni Maria Guazzo

IRFRI – Gruppo Forte, Salerno, Italy

Consiglia Nappo

IRFRI – Gruppo Forte, Salerno, Italy

Morena Ferraiuolo

CIPPS, Salerno, Italy

Abstract

Research in psychotherapy refers, almost exclusively, to outcomes, defining the changes achieved through treatment and studying what happens at the end of the process compared to the starting point (baseline). This treatment, however, is so complex that its evolution is unpredictable: slight variations in the initial conditions produce effects, even very significant ones, that are not deterministically linked to the conditions themselves. Therefore, to have a faithful representation of the change process, it is necessary to have an instrument that can detect the useful indicators significant for improving the therapist-patient relational modality for the duration of the therapy. An instrument that seems to satisfy these characteristics, even though it is still statistically insignificant, is the Questionnaire for the Evaluation of Psychotherapy (Q-EPT) designed and constructed by one of the authors (G.M.G.) that allows one to investigate the effectiveness of therapy during therapy itself, through the compilation of the areas: 1) Therapeutic relationship, 2) Therapy Motivation, 3) Therapy Adherence and 4) Outcomes. Preliminary results were appreciable in terms of both reliability (Inter-Class Confidence Interval = 0.78) and internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = 0.92).

Introduction

Psychotherapy as a science should be based on the following epistemological assumptions [1, 2]: 1) the psychotherapeutic process is an action aimed at behavioural change (covert and/or overt) that creates suffering and/or maladjustment, with specific goals determined by the therapist's theoretical model of reference; 2) the goals are pursued in each theoretical model using specific techniques (readable and repeatable from the outside to ensure the intersubjectivity of control); 3) the change is produced within a relationship between 'subjects' (therapists/clients) whose dimensions are assessable and explainable in both theoretical and real terms [3, 4].

In empirical studies in psychotherapy, when one speaks of research, one almost exclusively refers to outcomes, trying to define the changes achieved through treatment and studying what happens at the end of the treatment compared to the starting point (Baseline). The biggest problem lies in what is considered the

starting point, and one must only change the outcome indicator to get opposite results. One historically used indicator for verifying the intervention is the reduction of manifest symptoms. Still, this remission is not necessarily the only criterion for psychotherapy's 'good outcome'. Symptoms may indicate the presence of a pathological process but say little about the nature of the problem [5, 6].

The definition of the initial pathological state (clinical problem), therefore, must be somewhat isomorphic and congruent with the definition of the type of intervention applied (treatment) and with the definition of what is expected to be changed at the end of the treatment concerning the initial problem (outcome), investigating several levels simultaneously [7]:

Level I (Symptomatic). Although particularly complex, symptom reduction remains the preferred criterion for defining a good treatment outcome in most published research.

More Information

How to cite this article: Guazzo GM, Nappo C, Ferraiuolo M. Preliminary Study on the Questionnaire for the Evaluation of Psychotherapy (Q-EPT). Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(6):4-11.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(6).01

Keywords:

Assessment,
Psychotherapy Evaluation,
Therapist-patient relationship,
Change processes.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Level II (Adaptation). The measurement of the patient's relational quality of life is confronted with a wide range of events and situations, which makes the use of several indicators necessary in this area as well.

Level III (Functioning). Mental functioning depends on both symptomatology and contextual adaptation.

Level IV (Contextual). The set of contextual situations (family, community, etc.) that have a direct influence, positive or negative, on the subject's life.

Level V (Satisfaction). The degree of satisfaction perceived by the patient (and possibly by the family members) [3].

As can be deduced from what has been said, psychotherapeutic treatment is so complex as to make its evolution unpredictable: slight variations in the initial conditions produce effects, even very relevant ones, that are not deterministically linked to the conditions themselves. Therefore, to have a faithful representation of the process of change, it is necessary to have a measuring instrument that, for the entire duration of the therapy, can detect the useful indicators that are significant for improving the therapist-patient relational modality, which often represents the most important and determining factor for effective psychotherapy [8, 9, 10].

For this reason, the Questionnaire for the Evaluation of Psychotherapy (Q-EPT) was devised and constructed, which not only assesses outcomes but also the therapist-patient interaction based on three parameters: relationship, motivation and adherence to therapy, sharing the opinion that psychotherapists, despite having different theoretical models of reference, must, in any case, share a common language and methodology in the evaluation of psychotherapy.

Method

Questionnaire design

The choice of the items was made through four distinct phases:

Phase 1. Analysis of the scientific literature on the evaluation of psychotherapy.

Phase 2. Interpretation of the data collected and indication of the subjects to whom the questionnaire was administered in the pre-test phase.

Phase 3. The items are divided into four areas: a) Therapeutic Relationship, b) Therapy Motivation, c) Therapy Adherence, and d) Outcomes.

Phase 4. Experimental administration to a sample of subjects for psychometric evaluation.

Implementing these phases reduced the ambiguity margins of the items as much as possible while favouring a more precise psychotherapy assessment.

For the coding of the test answers, a 4-point numerical Likert scale (0 to 3) was chosen where '0' corresponds to 'NEVER', '1' to 'SOMETIMES', '2' to 'OFTEN' and '3' to 'ALWAYS'.

The Q-EPT aims to investigate the therapy's effectiveness by completing areas 1-3 of the questionnaire administered to the patients during the therapy (areas 1-3 from the third session to which area 4 is added from the eighth session). In this way, feedback on the treatment progress can be obtained, and, if necessary, decisions can be made to modify the interventions according to the patient's needs. Providing the therapists with feedback on the progress of the therapy allows them to monitor changes in the patient in the following areas:

- *Therapeutic Relationship*, or therapeutic alliance, indicates, within a psychotherapeutic process, the mutual agreement that is established between patient and therapist regarding the goals of change, the tasks necessary to achieve these goals, and the establishment of a bond aimed at maintaining an active collaboration between the parties, based on trust and mutual acceptance [11]. Many clinicians and researchers [12, 13, 14] point out that this relationship is a common factor across the various psychotherapeutic orientations and one of the most reliable predictors of outcome.

- *Therapy Motivation* refers to the patient's intention to change or revise certain behaviours or beliefs to obtain significant positive results. Each person may have a certain degree of readiness to change when entering psychotherapy, which may be influenced by anxiety or fear of change, the degree of rigidity of one's beliefs and the effectiveness of the psychotherapy or the psychotherapist [15, 16].

- *Therapy Adherence*, a vital element of the therapeutic act, is the patient's 'adherence' to the psychotherapist's suggestions and prescriptions (compliance), which has the idea of a genuine therapeutic alliance and sharing. The patient's compliance with psychotherapy represents one of the most critical problems in clinical practice since the success of any intervention depends on the patient's effective adherence to the therapy. Non-compliance with treatment has direct consequences, such as the inadequacy of the treatment and the emergence of problems related to the ineffective management of the pathology. The first step, then, to reduce the extent of non-adherence is a greater awareness of its importance on the part of the patient through improved communication and more excellent knowledge of the underlying problems [17].

- *Outcomes*, in psychotherapy, are defined as the assessment (before, during and after the provision of a therapeutic service) of the patients' behaviour, emotional states and adaptation, which are related to why they sought psychological therapy. It is fundamental in psychotherapeutic treatment to increase the degree of knowledge on how to provide increasingly appropriate services in response to

treatment needs, considering that meta-analyses highlight how the Effect Size (a statistical measure of the potential of treatment) of psychotherapy is superior to other medical treatments [18, 19].

Thus, a sudden reduction in relationship, motivation, or adherence can be identified early to allow the psychotherapist to modify his intervention to the patient’s needs, overcome his biases, and improve

treatment outcomes. Based on these considerations, it is possible to identify the level of the areas investigated (Therapeutic Relationship, Therapy Motivation, Therapy Adherence and Outcomes) by transcribing the data collected with the Questionnaire (Appendix 1) in Tables 1 and 2, from which it is then possible to identify the degree of Efficacy of the therapy (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2):

Table 1: Report the Scores from the Questionnaire (Appendix 1) in the Table Divided into the Four Areas Considered and Report the Sum of the Scores in the Square to the Right of Each Area

1. Therapeutic Relationship				
20. I have clear and comprehensible information about the therapy and how it works (costs, duration, etc.).	0	1	2	3
38. I have someone who listens to me and speaks to me in a calm and balanced tone of voice	0	1	2	3
13. I express my thoughts freely, without being subjected to any conditioning	0	1	2	3
28. I have established a cordial relationship, but it cannot be described as friendly	0	1	2	3
36. The therapeutic approach and areas of expertise were clearly explained to me	0	1	2	3
34. I share the various stages of the psychotherapy project	0	1	2	3
07. I ask for explanations about the techniques indicated by the therapist	0	1	2	3
30. I establish an empathic relationship with the therapist (listens to what I say with interest, etc.)	0	1	2	3
16. I feel comfortable with the therapist	0	1	2	3
29. I feel helped to understand my behaviour better, without feeling judged	0	1	2	3
2. Therapy Motivation				
02. I addressed with the therapist the difficulties that arose during therapy	0	1	2	3
03. I contact the therapist, if needed, for advice between therapies	0	1	2	3
05. I give notice in time in case of unexpected absences or delays	0	1	2	3
31. I always respect the agreed time and manner of payment	0	1	2	3
32. I agree with the therapist on the goals to be pursued with psychotherapy	0	1	2	3
10. I carry out accurately the ‘tasks’ suggested by the therapist	0	1	2	3
08. I feel free to choose what to address in therapy and when to do it	0	1	2	3
37. I have enough space to express myself and be heard	0	1	2	3
25. I look for information everywhere (internet, books, magazines, etc.) about my problem	0	1	2	3
33. I compare myself, with respect to therapy, with my general practitioner, relatives, friends, etc.	0	1	2	3
3. Therapy Adherence				
35. I feel I can trust the therapist who is on my side	0	1	2	3
18. I am satisfied with my psychotherapy course	0	1	2	3
04. I have a greater appreciation of my needs	0	1	2	3
26. I am aware of some aspects of myself that I did not grasp before	0	1	2	3
15. I feel I am listened to with interest and understood by the therapist	0	1	2	3
24. I feel actively and collaboratively involved in therapy	0	1	2	3
12. I reach my own conclusions through reflection	0	1	2	3
22. I put the techniques I have been advised into practice immediately	0	1	2	3
40. I often experience very strong emotions during therapy	0	1	2	3
11. I feel helped to discover and develop my abilities to become autonomous and responsible	0	1	2	3
4. Outcomes (not to be considered if the PsT started less than 8 sessions ago)				
01. I implement, in daily life, new behaviours that I have identified during therapy	0	1	2	3
06. The feedback I receive from relatives and friends are indicators of a regained psychological wellbeing	0	1	2	3
21. I make choices autonomously, evaluating all options adequately	0	1	2	3

19. I can better control repetitive and/or impulsive behaviour that was previously out of control	0	1	2	3
17. I can express my wishes, opinions and emotions to others	0	1	2	3
09. I can propose myself and can decline others' offers	0	1	2	3
14. I feel able to cope with life's challenges and difficulties without the need to resort to others	0	1	2	3
27. I am more compassionate towards others, even if they have caused me sorrow	0	1	2	3
39. I feel more comfortable in various life contexts and am more confident about the future	0	1	2	3
23. If I felt the need, I would return to psychotherapy	0	1	2	3

Table 2: The Sums in the Squares with the Highlighted Sides of Each Area

Q-EPT	PO	PMO	CrE
1. Therapeutic Relationship (7,13,16,20,28,29,30,34,36,38)		30	
2. Therapy Motivation (2,3,5,8,10,25,31,32,33,37)			
3. Therapy Adherence (4,11,12,15,18,22,24,26,35,40)			
4. Outcomes (1,6,9,14,17,19,21,23,27,39)			

ΣPO CrE

[CrE = (ΣPO/120) x 100]

Tab. 2 - The sums in the squares with the highlighted sides of each area (Therapeutic Relationship, Therapy Motivation, Therapy Adherence and Outcomes) are reported in the 'PO' column, then divided by 30 (Maximum Obtainable Score) and multiplied by 100, the result is transcribed in the 'CrE' column (Efficacy

Criterion), the meaning of which is highlighted in Fig. 1. On the right-hand side of the table, the efficacy of the therapy (CrE) is calculated by entering the sum of the 'PO' in the 'ΣPO' box, and the formula CrE = (ΣPO/120) x 100 is applied. The result is then transcribed in the 'CrE' box, the meaning of which is highlighted in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: Administration of the Reduced Questionnaire, to be Carried Out After the Third Session

Fig. 1 – Administration of the Reduced Questionnaire (Appendix 1, but when scoring, consider only the items in areas 1-3 of Tab. 2), to be carried out after the third session; this modality should be adopted to allow the therapist and the patient to familiarize themselves and share the emotional experience. The evaluation of the

scores achieved for each area, as can be seen from the figure, is expressed with 4 'judgements': 'EXCELLENT' if the score is equal to or greater than 80%, 'GOOD' if it is between 50% and 79%, 'SUFFICIENT' if it is between 25% and 49%, and 'LOW' if it is less than 24%.

Figure 2: Administration of the Entire Questionnaire after the Eighth Session

Fig. 2 – Administration of the entire questionnaire (Appendix 1) after the eighth session. The evaluation of the overall score on the effectiveness of the therapy, as

can be seen from the figure, is expressed with 4 'judgements': 'Effective' if the score is 80% or more, 'Enough Effective' if it is between 50% and 79%, 'Little

Effective' if it is between 25% and 49%, and 'Not Effective' if it is less than 24%. After the first administration (after the eighth session), the complete questionnaire can be administered a few more times to monitor the progress of the therapy.

Participants

The sample taken into consideration for this preliminary study consisted of 182 patients undergoing treatment at many psychotherapy studios in the Campania Region of different orientations (Cognitive-Behavioural, Strategic and Systemic-Relational), aged between 24-57 years (M=42), of whom 107 were female and 75 males, with diagnoses, in most cases, of Depression, Obsessive Compulsive Disorder, Anxiety Disorders, Phobias and Gender Identity).

Patients were given a brief oral explanation of the questionnaire and asked to evaluate their experience in psychotherapy.

Pre-test

In the construction phase of the instrument, an examination of the internal coherence of the items (item analysis) concerning the various areas under investigation was administered to 40 adult patients undergoing psychotherapeutic treatment in various professional practices to verify the clarity and appropriateness of the items, listed in a randomized manner, and to obtain, in the event of difficulties, indications for a linguistic and functional revision of the items.

The Psychotherapy Evaluation Questionnaire (Q-EPT) was drawn up at the end of this process. It consists of 40 items and is subdivided into 4 areas, three of which analyze the progress of psychotherapy and one of its outcomes (Appendix 1).

Results

Test-retest reliability and internal consistency

For the test-retest analysis, the questionnaire was administered to the entire sample. The data were analysed using the Interclass Confidence Interval (ICI), giving encouraging results with a value of 0.80 (p < 0.01) [21].

Internal consistency, assessed through Cronbach's alpha, showed values in an interval between 0.87 and 0.94 and is statistically significant for the entire sample and the individual areas. The results are presented in Tab. 3.

Table 3: Evaluation of the Internal Consistency of the Questionnaire Using Cronbach's Alpha

Areas	Cronbach's alpha
All SS	0,92
Relationship	0.94
Motivation	0.90
Adherence	0.89
Outcomes	0,87

Conclusions

Our study aimed to examine the reliability and internal consistency of the questionnaire one of the authors (G.M.G.) created to evaluate the psychotherapeutic intervention.

The questionnaire achieved a good reliability rating using the Interclass Confidence Interval, with a score of 0.78. Indeed, the patients did not substantially change their answers one week later.

The most satisfactory results regarding the psychometric evaluation of the questionnaire are those related to its internal consistency. These values are very high for all the subjects who participated in the study: 0.92 Cronbach's alpha, while they fall slightly for the Outcome area (0.87 Cronbach's alpha). A high value in this aspect indicates a high coherence of the questionnaire, which is a fundamental element for effectively measuring the phenomenon under investigation [5].

The subjects were motivated to evaluate psychotherapy using the Likert scale to its full extent. The Q-EPT is a quick instrument to administer. It took less than 30 minutes to complete and was easy to understand, as the subjects did not leave any questions unanswered.

However, the study has several limitations:

- a numerically small sample to question, in an exhaustive manner, the outcomes of psychotherapy, although it may be helpful to gather information on what happens (or has happened) during treatment (concerning variables such as the relationship with the therapist, the feeling of the effectiveness of the therapy, satisfaction concerning expectations, etc.) and to consider the objectives, which were identified when the clinical project was formulated: remission (total or partial remission of symptoms), modification of certain aspects of personality functioning, partial or total resolution of a possible nodal motive, acquisition of better-coping strategies, an increase in subjective well-being, an increase in social skills and the prevention of a 'crisis' or flare-up of symptoms;
 - the importance of carrying out an Exploratory Factor Analysis to highlight which items saturate the factors and how many dimensions the instrument consists of;
 - identification of cut-offs ('Effective' if the score is 80% or more, 'Enough Effective' if it is between 50% and 79%, 'Little Effective' if it is between 25% and 49%, and 'Not Effective' if it is less than 24%) using ROC CURVES.
- The instrument is hoped to be studied with a larger sample and a more appropriate and meaningful statistical analysis. At the same time, it can provide a clear and straightforward evaluation of the psychotherapeutic course. The psychotherapist can use it as food for thought to improve his performance.

References

- [1] Di Nuovo S, Lo Verso G, Giannone F, Di Blasi M, editors. *Valutare le Psicoterapie. La Ricerca Italiana*. Milano: Angeli; 1998.
- [2] Di Nuovo S. La ricerca in psicoterapia: alcune riflessioni sulla scientificità. *Rivista di Psicologia*. 2007;1:10–7.
- [3] Guazzo GM. La ricerca scientifica in psicoterapia. In: Sessa F, editor. *La psicoterapia strategica ad orientamento neuroscientifico. Teorie e applicazioni in contesti clinici e non clinici*. San Cesario, LE: Pensa; 2023. p. 179–213.
- [4] Eysenck HJ. *The Effects of Psychotherapy*. New York: International Science Press; 1966.
- [5] Kazdin AE, Kendall PC. Current progress and future plans for developing effective treatments: Comments and perspective. *J Clin Child Psychol*. 1998;27:217–26. doi: 10.1207/s15374424jccp2702_8
- [6] Luccio R. *Ricerca e analisi dei dati in psicologia*. Vol. 1–2. Bologna: Il Mulino; 2005.
- [7] Hoagwood K, Jensen PS, Pretti T, Burns BJ. Outcomes of mental health care for children and adolescents: I. A comprehensive conceptual model. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. 1996;35:1055–63. doi: 10.1097/00004583-199608000-00017
- [8] Fonagy P. The effectiveness of psychodynamic psychotherapies: an update. *World Psychiatry*. 2015;14:137–50. doi: 10.1002/wps.20235
- [9] Roth A, Fonagy P. *What Works for Whom? A Critical Review of Psychotherapy Research*. New York: Guilford Press; 2004.
- [10] Del Re AC, Fluckiger C, Horvath AO, Symonds D, Wampold BE. Therapist effects in the therapeutic alliance-outcome relationship: a restricted-maximum likelihood meta-analysis. *Clin Psychol Rev*. 2012;32:642–9. doi: 10.1016/j.cpr.2012.07.002
- [11] Fava E, Pazzi E, Arduini L, Masserini C, Lammoglia M, Landra S, Pazzaglia P, Carta I. Gli effetti delle psicoterapie: uno studio sulla percezione che i pazienti hanno dei risultati dei loro trattamenti. *Ricerca in Psicoterapia*. 1998;1:324–43.
- [12] Luborsky L, Crits-Christoph P, Mintz J, Auerbach A. *Who Will Benefit from Psychotherapy? Predicting Therapeutic Outcomes*. New York: Basic Books; 1988.
- [13] Smith ML, Glass GV. Meta-analysis of psychotherapy outcome studies. *Am Psychol*. 1977;32(9):752–60. doi: 10.1037/0003-066X.32.9.752
- [14] Stiles WB, Shapiro DA, Elliott R. Are all psychotherapies equivalent? *Am Psychol*. 1986;41(2):165–80. doi: 10.1037/0003-066X.41.2.165
- [15] Van Beek N, Verhuel R. Motivation for treatment in patients with personality disorders. *J Pers Disord*. 2008;22(1):89–100.
- [16] Fava E, Masserini C. *Efficacia delle psicoterapie nel servizio pubblico: Il contributo della ricerca valutativa alla clinica*. Milano: Angeli; 2002.
- [17] Schmidt NB, Woolaway-Bickel K. The effects of treatment compliance on outcome in cognitive-behavioral therapy for panic disorder: Quality versus quantity. *J Consult Clin Psychol*. 2000;68(1):13–8. doi: 10.1037/0022-006X.68.1.13
- [18] Wampold BE. Methodological problems in identifying efficacious psychotherapies. *Psychother Res*. 1997;7:21–43.
- [19] Vidotto G, Ciuffi R. La verifica della psicoterapia. In: Galeazzi A, Meazzini P, editors. *Mente e comportamento*. Firenze: Giunti; 2004. p. 563–88.
- [20] Terwee CB, Bot SDM, de Boer MR, van der Windt DAWM, Knol DL, Dekker J, Bouter LM, de Vet HCW. Quality criteria were proposed for measurement properties of health status questionnaire. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2007;60(1):34–42. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2006.03.012
- [21] Weir JP. Quantifying test-retest reliability using the intraclass correlation coefficient and the SEM. *J Strength Cond Res*. 2005;19(1):231–40.

Appendix 1

Psychotherapist Initials: _____ Psychotherapy Orientation: _____

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE EVALUATION OF PSYCHOTHERAPY (Q-EPT)

Giovanni Maria Guazzo

First and last name initials: _____ Sex: [M] [F] Age: _____ Start of PsT from [3] [8] sessions Data: _____

Instructions: Below are some items for describing your own experience in psychotherapy. Read the descriptions carefully and choose the answer with which you most agree and tick the number in the right-hand column of the sheet: '0' corresponds to 'NEVER', '1' to 'SOME TIME', '2' to 'OFTEN' and '3' to 'ALWAYS'.

There are no right or wrong answers. Do not take too long to answer the questions and give the best answer to your experience.

© Giovanni Maria Guazzo

01. I implement, in daily life, new behaviours that I have identified during therapy	0	1	2	3
02. I have addressed with the therapist the difficulties that have arisen during therapy	0	1	2	3
03. I contact the therapist, if needed, for advice between therapies	0	1	2	3
04. Awareness leads me to take my needs into greater consideration	0	1	2	3
05. I give early warning in case of absences or unforeseen delays	0	1	2	3
06. The feedback I receive from family and friends are indicators of a newfound psychological well-being	0	1	2	3
07. I ask for clarification of the techniques indicated by the therapist	0	1	2	3
08. I feel free to choose what to address in therapy and when to do it.	0	1	2	3
09. I know how to propose myself and how to decline offers from others.	0	1	2	3
10. I carry out accurately the 'tasks' suggested by the therapist	0	1	2	3
11. I feel helped to discover and develop my abilities to become autonomous and responsible	0	1	2	3
12. I come to my own conclusions through reflection	0	1	2	3
13. I express my thoughts freely, without any conditioning	0	1	2	3
14. I feel able to cope with the challenges and difficulties of life without the need to rely on others	0	1	2	3
15. I feel I am listened to with interest and understood by the therapist	0	1	2	3
16. I feel comfortable with the therapist	0	1	2	3
17. I can express my wishes, opinions and emotions to others	0	1	2	3
18. I am satisfied with my psychotherapy process	0	1	2	3
19. I can better control repetitive and/or impulsive behaviour that was previously out of control	0	1	2	3
20. I have clear and comprehensible information about the therapy and how it works (costs, duration, etc.)	0	1	2	3
21. I make choices autonomously, evaluating all options adequately	0	1	2	3
22. I immediately put into practice the techniques I have been advised.	0	1	2	3
23. If I felt the need, I would return to psychotherapy	0	1	2	3
24. I feel actively and collaboratively involved in therapy	0	1	2	3
25. I look for information everywhere (internet, books, magazines, etc.) about my problem	0	1	2	3
26. I am aware of some aspects of myself that I did not see before	0	1	2	3
27. I am more compassionate towards others, even if they have caused me pain	0	1	2	3
28. I have established a cordial but not describable as friendly relationship	0	1	2	3
29. I feel helped to better understand my behaviour, without feeling judged	0	1	2	3
30. I have established an empathic relationship with the therapist (listens to what I say with interest, etc.)	0	1	2	3
31. I always respect the agreed time and manner of payment	0	1	2	3
32. I have agreed with the therapist on the goals to be pursued with psychotherapy	0	1	2	3
33. I discuss the therapy with the general practitioner, relatives, friends, etc.	0	1	2	3
34. I share the various phases of the psychotherapy project	0	1	2	3
35. I feel I can trust the therapist who is on my side	0	1	2	3
36. The therapeutic approach and areas of expertise are clearly explained to me	0	1	2	3

37. I have enough space to express myself and be heard	0	1	2	3
38. I have someone who listens to me and speaks to me in a calm and balanced tone of voice	0	1	2	3
39. I feel more comfortable in various contexts of life and am more confident about the future	0	1	2	3
40. I often experience very strong emotions during therapy	0	1	2	3

© Giovanni Maria Guazzo

